

A Review on Ayurvedic Poisonous Plants Their Shodhan Process and Medicinal Values

Vd. Amrita Baidya¹, Vd. Chaitanya Baraskar²

¹Assistant professor, Agadtantra Department, Shree Ayurved Mahavidyalaya Nagpur

²Associate professor, Agadtantra Department, Sardar patel Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Balaghat

ABSTRACT: A poisonous plant is one that when touched or consumed in large quantities, can be hazardous or lethal to humans or other animals. These plants can be utilized as herbal medicines with therapeutic effects when used in the right proportions and in small doses. Many plants are harmful to people when consumed or through skin contact with plant chemicals. Poisonous medicinal herbs are used to treat a variety of illness, including diabetes, cancer, infections and fungal growth. According to the review, numerous phytochemical components that have diuretic, purgative, laxative, anti-allergic and other significant therapeutic effects have been identified in a variety of medicinal plants. The shodhana process is the only bridge between visha and Aushadhi. Shodhana is the process by which physical, chemical, and natural impurities are removed. It will intensify the potency and effectiveness of the drug and nullify its toxicity. The aim of this review article is to provide a brief overview of the numerous medicinal uses of some poisonous plants.

KEYWORDS: Poisonous plant, Shodhana, Toxicity, Medicinal values

INTRODUCTION

In India different plants are used for the medicinal purposes. Some of them are poisonous plants which also have medicinal values. After proper purification they are used in many Ayurvedic formulations. It is mandatory to have proper knowledge of the poisonous plants which when used in well-mannered way, acts as a potent therapeutic agent. The toxicity could be in the form of higher concentration of the drug. The toxicity of the poisonous plants also varies in its form like some plant seeds are non poisonous if ingested directly and are poisonous if taken in chewable form. The poisoning could be in the form of ingestion, inhalation, absorption, contact poisoning etc^[1]. Poisonous plants are more common because they are used less frequently. If medical costs can be covered, the burden of effective medicines can be controlled to some extent^[2]. According to the principles of Ayurveda, even strong poisons can be effective medicines when taken correctly. On the other hand, even the most effective medicine can turn into poison if not used properly^[3]. According to Acharya Sushruta, there is no substance in the universe that does not have some form of healing. Medicines that treat disease or substances used in special combinations prove the existence of medicinal substance due to their good and powerful results^[4]. According to Acharya Charaka, if poison used in a therapeutic dose will provide results in a beneficial way to the patient^[5].

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Charaka explains the importance of shodhana while using plants as medicines and if used improperly is a fatal poison. Using as medicinal use must be used after process of purification (shodhana), which helps to

prevent the fatal effect of vishadravya and have important medicinal uses, so it is important to understand the process of Shodhana of Visha and Upvisha mentioned in Ayurvedic text^[6].

General Shodhana

- a) Gomutra Nimajjana
- b) Swedana
- c) Bharjana
- d) Bhavana
- e) Nisnehana
- f) Kshalana
- g) Nistwachkarana^[7]

Shodhana Of Visha Dravya

Vatsanabha (*Acotinum ferox*)

The roots of Vatsanabha were cut into small pieces and tied in pottali, it can be detoxified by placing it in cow's milk or goat milk in Dolayantra for 3-6 hrs. After that, pieces of Vatsanabh are washed with warm water and used for therapeutic purpose.

Shodhana of Upvisha Dravya (Sub-poisonous Drug)

1. **Ahiphen (*Papaver somniferum linn*)-**

The exhudate is dissolved in water, filtered with cloth, and then mixed with Godugdha (cow's milk), which is heated over a low flame. Ginger juice is then added to the paste, which is then thrice through and dried in the shade.

2. **Bhallataka (*Semicarpus anacardium linn*) (Seed)**

The top portion of Bhallataka fruits should be removed with a knife and mixed with brick powder before being placed in a pottali (bag) and tied at the mouth with thread. When the brick powder becomes wet with oil, this is gently rubbed by hands, and the skin of the Bhallataka is unwrapped and washed with hot water to produce shudh Bhallataka.

3. **Bhanga (*Cannabis Sativa linn*) (Except seed)**

Leaves are tied in a cloth and soaked in water; the process must be repeated until the discharge of a greenish hue stops.

4. **Dhatu (Dhatu Metal linn)**

Seeds are preserved in potallis and Swedana (Fometed) in Dolayantra by adding Godugdha (cow's milk), Gomutra (cow's urine) for three hours. Once that, seeds are washed with warm water and dried in sun. The seeds are used after the seed coat has been removed.

5. **Gunja (*Abrus precartorius linn*)**

Seeds are tied in two layers of fabric and suspended in Godugdha, Gomutra or kanji any of these- For Swedan taken in Dolyantra. The suspension is then boiled with Gunja seeds, which are then removed, cleaned in hot water, dried and preserved.

6. **Jaipala (*Croton Tiglium*)**

Remove the physical imperfections of seeds by washing them with water, drying them in the shade afterward, and removing the outer covering. Next, the cotyledons are gently divided to remove the radicle with a knife. Seeds are knotted in pottalia and put through three rounds of swedsns using Godugdha (cow's milk)

7. **Karveera (*Nerium indicum*)**

Swedana technique is used to purify the roots of karveera. The roots are cleaned with water and dried in Dolayantra after being soaked in Godugdha (cow's milk) for three hours after Shodhana.

8. Langli (Glosiosa Superba Linn)

Fresh Langli roots and seeds are soaked in cow's urine for 24 hours before being washed with lukewarm water to detoxify them.

9. Snuhi (Euphorbia nerrifolia Linn)

Snuhi milk is gathered, combined with Imli (Tamarind) juice, placed in a container, and let to dry in direct sunlight. Once properly dried, it should be used.

10. Kuchala (Strychnos Nuxvomica)

For seven nights, the seeds of the kuchala plant must be submerged in fresh cow urine (Gomutra). It is then taken off and rinsed with water.

The seed coat and embryo are removed and the cotyledons are placed in Goghrit (cow's ghee) and powdered cells before the seeds are further detoxified by swedana boiling with Godugdha (cow's milk) in Dolayantra for three hours^[8].

Table 1: List of Various plants Metioned in schedule(1) of the drugs and cosmetics act, 1940 used in Ayurved ^[9]

Sr. No.	Visha Dravya (Poisonous plant)	Latin Name
1	Ahiphena (Except seeds)	Papaver somiferum Linn
2	Arka	Calotropis procera
3	Bhallataka	Semecarpus anacardium
4	Bhanga (Except seeds)	Cannabis sativa
5	Danti	Baliospermum montanum
6	Dhatura	Dhatura metal
7	Gunja (seed)	Abrus precartorius
8	Jaipal (seed)	Croton tiglium
9	Karaveera	Nerium indicum
10	Langali	Gloriosa superba
11	Parasaki yavani	Hyoscyamus niger
12	Shringi Yavani	Acontium chasmanthum stapf
13	Vatsanabha	Acontium chasmanthum stapf
14	Vishamushti	Strychnox nuxvomica

Table 2: List of POISONOUS PLANTS AS PER Ayurveda with their indication and Formulation ^[10-12]

Sr. No.	Visha Dravya (Poisonous plants)	Therapeutic Uses/ Action	Formulations
1	Ahiphen (Except seeds)	Dhatu Shoshaka, Grahi, Kaphaghna, Vata-pitta karaka	Ahiphenasava, Nidrodaya vati, Karpurarasa, Mahavataraj Rasa
2	Arka (Rakta and Shukla)	Udaroga kustha, Kandru, Vrana, Pliharoga, Gulma, Arsa, Krimiroga	Abhaya Lavana, Arka Lavana
3	Bhallataka	Shukrala, Vata-Sleshmahara, Udara, Anaha, Kustha, Grahani, Gulma, Jwara, Switra, Agnimandya, Krimi, Vrana	Bhallatka Rasayana, Amrita Bhallataka, Bhallatak Taila, Tilarushkar Yoga
4	Bhanga (Except seeds)	Grahi, Kaphaghna, Pachana, Moha, Mada, Vaakvardhak, Agnivardhana	Jatiphaladi churna, Madananda Modak

5	Danti	Deepana, Gudaankur, Ashmari, Shoola, Rakta Vikara, Kandu, Kustha, Vidaha, Sotha, Udar Roga, Kriminashaka	Dantyadyarishta, Punarnava Mandura, Abhayarishta, Kaakayana Gutika, Dantiharitaki
6	Dhatura	Jwaraghna, Kusthaghna, Yuka Liksha Nashhaka, Krimi and Vishapaha	Kankasava, Sutshekharrasa, Jwarankush rasa
7	Gunja (seed)	Keshya, Vata-pitta-jwara Nashaka, Relives Mukhashosha, Bhrama, Shwasa, Trishna and mada, Netra Rogahara, Vrishya Balya, Kandughna	Gunjabhadra Rasa
8	Jaipala (seed)	Krimihar, Virechak, Deepan, Kapha Vataghna, Jalodara Nashak	Ichhabhedi Rasa, Jalodaradi Rasa, Jwarmurari rasa
9	Karaveera	Vrana Laghavkar, Nterakopa, Kustha, Krimi, Vrana, Kandughna	Karveeraadya Taila
10	Langali	Kustha, Krimi, Arsha, Vrana, Shoola, Garbhapatana,	Kasheesadi Taila, Langali Rasayana
11	Parasika Yavani	Pachana, Ruchya, Grahi, Madakari	Parashiyadi Churna
12	Shringi Visha	Rasayana, Yogavahi, Tridoshaghna, Veeryavardhana, Kustha, Sotha Nashaka, Madhumeha Hara	Ananda Bhairava Rasa, Mrutunjaya Rasa, Jwarmurari rasa, Rambana Rasa
13	Vatsanabh	Vataroga, Sannipata, Vatakaphajvara, Jvartisara, Kanharoga	Tribhuvankirtirasa, Anandabhairava rasa, Sutashekhar rasa, Vaatavidhwansa rasa
14	Vishamushti	Madkari, Vyathakar, Grahi, Rakta vikara	Agnitundi vati, vishamushti vati, krimimudgarasa, laxmivilasrasa

CONCLUSION

Ayurveda is an ancient and renowned medicinal pathy of ancient India. Even the poisonous plants have been used for medicinal purpose in Ayurveda. Acharyas use many toxic natural drugs either in their crude form or after shodhana processes for treating human diseases. As we know that even a strong poison can be converted to an excellent medicine if processed and administered properly but if handled incorrectly, it may become hazardous. Poisonous plants have numerous medicinal values. Certain precautions about those plants are enough to use these poisonous plants for medication purposes. This study conclude that by doing proper shodhana process these poisonous plants can be used in the diseases. These toxic herbs are employed in a variety of compositions with special care. Many Ayurvedic preparations which are made with these plants shows great results in multiple disorders. The proper awareness of toxicity and usefulness of these poisonous plants are the main concern in present day scenario.

REFERENCES

1. Tamilselvan N et al, A review on some poisonous plants and their medicinal values, ELSEVIER/2014/Vol.3/ Issue 2. P85-8
2. Dr. Ashish Bharti Goswami. A Survey Of Visha Dravya (Poisonous plants) and Vishaghna Dravya Antidotal plants) in and around Belgaum Region [PG thesis]., KLE university; 2010.
3. Acharya J T. Varanasi: Chawkhamba Vidyabhawan; International Journal Of Unani and Integrative Medicine <http://www.unanijournal.com>- 91-Agnivesha: Charaka Samhita; 2011.p.23.

4. Trikamji Yadavji, Sushruta Samhita. Varansi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan.Sutrasthana 41/9;2003.
5. Charaka Samhita. Yadavji Trikamji Acharya, editor. Varanasi: Chowkhamba Krishnadas Academy; 2006. Chikitsasthana
6. Concept Of Mahavisha –Upvisha Shodhana In Agadtantra. Dahegaonkar Yogesh Anand. March 2020.
7. <https://www.nhp.gov.in/visha-upvisha-metals-in> -ayurveda-mtl
8. Concept Of Mahavisha-Upvisha Shodhana In Agadtantra. Dahegaonkar Yogesh Anand. March 2020.
9. National AIDS control organization [Internet]. Naco.gov;2019[cited 2024 Apr 14]. Available from: <http://www.naco.gov.in/sites/default/files/Drug%20%26%20Cosmetic%20Act%201940-1.pdf>
10. Sharma PV. Dravyaguna Vigyan (Vedic plants and history of Dravyaguna); Vol.4, Reprint. Varanasi: Chaukhamba bharti academy; 2014.p.19, 433,166,25,426,500,770,211,603,51,106
11. Bhavmishra, Bhavprakash Nighantu. Reprint. Chunekar KC, Varanasi; Chaukhamba bharti Academy ;2013.
12. Anonymous. Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India, New Delhi: Govt. of India, Ministry of Health of Family Welfare;2004.